

COMICS STYLE IN TEACHING LITERATURE AND THE READING PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on determining the difference of comics style in teaching literature and the reading performance of the students. Grade five pupils in Cabay Elementary School, in Tiaong II District, Tiaong, Quezon, were chosen as the respondents of the study. The pre – test and post - test was used as the main data-gathering instrument, consists of two main parts: the profile of the respondents such as age, and gender and the reading test in terms of comprehension, vocabulary and general knowledge. Preparatory measures were conducted before the implementation of the study, and several permission letters were also prepared. The test materials had been validated and corrected by external and internal experts. The result of some variables showed no significant difference between the pre – test and post - test of the reading performance after using comics style stories. As for the recommendations, the District Supervisor may use the study as a basis for planning reading intervention, the School Head may be aware of using different reading materials to enhance the reading performance of the learners, the teachers may craft their teaching materials that uplift the reading performance of the learners, the pupils may be aware of their reading performance in English, the future researchers may conduct a similar study in line with this program.

Keywords: comic style stories, comprehension, vocabulary, general knowledge, reading performance